

Study and analysis of tourist facilities of Jizzakh region

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Abstract:

This article discusses the issues of tourism facilities and investment potential of Jizzakh region.

Keywords: Jizzakh region, international investment forum, Bakhmal district, Zaamin district, sanatorium "Zomin",

EASIJ

Accepted 25 August 2020

Published 31 August 2020

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4031385

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On August 29-30, 2018, the International Investment Forum was held in Jizzakh. The purpose of this event, which is held for the first time in the history of the region, was to demonstrate the investment potential of Jizzakh and to organize a national exhibition of manufacturers.

The Jizzakh Investment Forum was attended by about 300 participants from 28 countries, including Belarus, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, UAE, Israel, India, Spain, Latvia, China, Russia, Turkey, Singapore, USA, South Korea and Japan.¹

At the International Investment Forum in Jizzakh, special attention was paid to increasing the tourism potential of the region.

In particular, the ecotourism potential of Zaamin and Bakhmal districts of Jizzakh region was fully demonstrated. Foreign guests visited local attractions such as Sher spring and Bobo-walnut. Projects prepared by local authorities and the Tourism Development Committee were also presented. The presented projects envisage the development of tourism in the region in three main areas: eco-tourism, agritourism and ethnic tourism.

It was decided to allocate land in Bakhmal and Zaamin districts for the construction of infrastructure needed for the implementation of these projects. For example, 2,000 hectares of land will be allocated for the development of ecotourism. The project envisages the organization of ecological trails in the area, horseback riding, donkey and quad biking, construction of funiculars, a ski resort, a restaurant and information center, a museum and shops selling local handicrafts.

5,000 hectares of land will be allocated for agritourism. Holiday homes, sports complexes, and nurseries for the conservation of rare animal and plant species will be built on the site. Honey farms will also be established. Here, tourists will be able to take part in agricultural activities such as camel rides, watching the kupkari game, picking fruit, and mowing the lawn.²

Modern hotels, children's resorts, campsites, balloon flight centers will be built to develop the ethno-tourist area. Tourists visiting this area will have the opportunity to see rural areas, historical and cultural monuments, natural monuments, archeological sites, national traditions. Tourists will also have the opportunity to learn the secrets of national crafts and national cuisine.

Among the tourist facilities of Jizzakh region, the sanatorium "Zomin" is of special importance. The sanatorium is one of the most popular places of rest and treatment in the Republic. The cool and temperate fresh air, the mountain forest covered with pine trees, the richness of medicinal fragrant plants, mountain animals give a special charm to nature.

Sanatorium "Zaamin" is located 50 km from the district center, a climatic resort in Jizzakh region, in the northern foothills of the Turkestan ridge, at an altitude of 2000 m above sea level, in the territory of the reserve among the pine forests. Due to this, the atmospheric pressure in the air is relatively low, the richness of oxygen and ultraviolet light from the sun is precisely adapted to the treatment of patients with diseases of the upper respiratory tract and nervous system.

¹ https://sputniknews-uz.com/trend/jizzaxdagi_xalqaro_forum/

² There.

The sanatorium consists of a modern 7-storey building located on a mountain slope. On the 1st and 2nd floors of the building there is a treatment department, kitchen, reception, administration. The treatment department is equipped with modern diagnostic and treatment equipment and employs 40 qualified nurses and 15 doctors of the highest category. The laboratory-diagnostic room has ultrasound, ECG, dentistry, gynecology rooms.

Vacationers admitted to the registry will be re-examined by specialists and laboratory-diagnostic examinations, re-diagnosed and treated.

Physiotherapy factors are widely used in treatment. These include high and low frequency currents, paraffin, massage, ultraviolet rays. In addition, 2 indoor baths, saunas, medicinal, pearl baths, various showers, underwater massages, mud treatments, baths with pine needles, spruce iodine-bromine salts are widely used.

Given that the sanatorium is adapted to the treatment of respiratory diseases, the artificial microclimate is treated with fine-grained sodium chloride salt (galotherapy) and extensive use of inhalation apparatus imported from Germany, allowing patients to recover quickly. Infusions made from medicinal plants with medicinal antibiotics are used by spray treatment, ie by the method of inhalation.

There are 2 exercise halls for morning therapeutic gymnastics, and the instructor conducts classes in 5 different groups of patients.

In the kitchen, dietetic meals are ordered by a doctor-nutritionist and a nurse, and diet tables are set. The kitchen is renovated and equipped in a modern look for 500 people.

Figure 1. The territory of the sanatorium "Zomin".

Now the sanatorium "Zomin", which has become the most magnificent resort of the Federation of Trade Unions of Uzbekistan, was built in the late seventies of the last century as a result of the efforts of Sharof Rashidov.

On the way to the sanatorium "Zaamin", you will see another newly built recreation center. The Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Combine built and put into operation this magnificent six-storey resort, which was restored with the direct initiative and encouragement of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Among the employees of the plant there are

people who have contributed to the science, literature, art, spirituality and enlightenment of the republic, as well as to the national economy. The camp, decorated with a variety of rare trees and wildflowers, such as linden, linden, oak, and pavloniya, is unique in Central Asia.

The territory of the sanatorium "Zomin" can be used for tourism purposes. For this purpose, some work has been partially organized by the administration of the sanatorium.

Figure 2. Ecological objects of the territory of the sanatorium "Zomin".

For example, once a week, a minibus tour is organized in the areas up to the border with Tajikistan, 10 km from the sanatorium. Along the route there is an opportunity to see such beautiful views of the mountains, the millennium arch, the field yard of Sh. Rashidov. Unfortunately, full information about these facilities is not provided and there is no approved travel route passport for this route either. This means that the revenue from this tour service is not shown anywhere.

As a result of the study and analysis of tourist facilities in Jizzakh region, the following recommendations can be made:

- Development of a tourism cluster to develop the ecotourism potential of Zaamin and Bakhmal districts of Jizzakh region;
- Attracting investors to projects developed by local authorities and the Tourism Development Committee;
- granting benefits to foreign investors and legal justification of their activities;
- Wide study of the potential of the sanatorium "Zaamin" and the effective use of existing opportunities;
- Creation of scientifically based routes to ecotourism facilities of Zaamin and Bakhmal districts (technological map, Afar-route passport, calculation, etc.).

Cite this article: Cite this article:

Author(s), AMRIDDINOVA R.S. (2020). “ Study and analysis of tourist facilities of Jizzakh region”, **Name of the Journal:** Euro Afro Studies International Journal, (EASIJ.COM), P, 199 – 204. DOI: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4031385 , Special Issue, Issue: 2, Vol.: 2, Article: 24, Month: August, Year: 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.easij.com/all-issues/>

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